

THE EFFECTS OF VSWR ON CONNECTOR SHIELDING
EFFECTIVENESS MEASUREMENTS IN A MODE-STIRRED CHAMBER

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Abstract

It is generally accepted among users of mode-stirred chambers that VSWR differences between a test sample and a reference measurement antenna can affect the measured shielding effectiveness (SE) of the test sample. In this study a connector was tested in two fixtures having different VSWR characteristics. Two different methods were used with each fixture, one which corrects for VSWR differences and one which does not. This study compares the results obtained using each method and fixture in order to determine how VSWR differences affect connector shielding measurements in the 1-10 GHz range.

Introduction

The specification for connector testing, MIL-STD-1344 Method 3008 [1], requires that the VSWR of the connector/test fixture assembly be measured but does not state how the information should be used. Other standards, such as the EIA Standard [2] and some European standards, specify a maximum allowable VSWR for the test fixture and measurement system. The EIA Standard also has detailed information on VSWR and how it affects measurements at each position of the mode stirrer. MIL-STD-1344 Method 3008 is presently being updated by the author of this paper with the intent of making it understandable and usable for all test labs having varying degrees of equipment sophistication. It is important to determine how VSWR actually affects the SE measurements of connectors in order to best incorporate corrections for VSWR into the specification.

There are two factors which contribute to the VSWR of an antenna or connector/test fixture in a mode-stirred chamber. One is the reflected energy within the device itself before it is radiated into the chamber. The second is the reflected energy from the chamber surfaces back into the antenna or connector under test (CUT). This second factor adds to the field strength in the chamber before returning to the antenna or CUT. These two factors became evident while comparing the VSWR measurements of a connector/test fixture in the mode-stirred chamber to its VSWR in an anechoic chamber. In the anechoic chamber the VSWR was somewhat lower. Corrections to the SE measurements for the second factor of the measured VSWR would actually add an error to the results since it adds to the field strength in the chamber. However, it is difficult to determine exactly how much each factor contributes to the VSWR of a connector/test fixture or antenna at each stirrer position.

The S parameters of two antennas in a mode-stirred chamber for each position of the stirrer were measured by Michael O. Hatfield of NSWC Dahlgren [3]. A log periodic antenna was used to transmit and a conical log spiral was used to receive. Figures 1 and 2 show the maximum, minimum, and average VSWR for the S11 and S22 parameters, respectively. Also shown in each graph is the VSWR when S21 is a minimum, i.e., when there is maximum pickup by the receive antenna. This occurs when peak measurements are taken by the receiving device (typically a spectrum analyzer). The peak measurements are used to determine SE. As seen in Figures 1 and 2, this VSWR is generally less than the average VSWR, indicating that VSWR effects on the SE measurements are relatively small.

A practical study was then performed to determine to what extent VSWR affects SE measurements. In this study, a connector was tested in two different fixtures with very different VSWR characteristics. Two different test methods were used, one which corrects for VSWR differences and one which does not. The shielding repeatability of a connector was also investigated. This study compares the results obtained using each method and fixture.

Test Method

The two fixtures used were both in accordance with MIL-STD-1344 Method 3008. Fixture 1 had a maximum measured VSWR of approximately 3:1, and Fixture 2 had a maximum VSWR of approximately 5:1.

The two methods used were the Receive Method and the Transmit Method as follows. The Receive Method is the method required by MIL-STD-1344 Method 3008, where a transmit antenna is used to produce a field in the chamber and the power received by the CUT is compared to the power received by a reference antenna. The shielding effectiveness is determined by:

$$SE = 10 \log \left[\frac{P_{REF}}{P_{input REF}} \bigg/ \frac{P_{CUT}}{P_{input CUT}} \right]$$

Where $P_{input REF}$ is the input power to the transmit antenna during reference measurements; $P_{input CUT}$ is the input power to the transmit antenna during connector measurements; P_{REF} is the power received by the reference antenna; and P_{CUT} is the power received by the CUT.

In the Transmit Method, the reference antenna transmits into the chamber and its reflected power is measured. The power received by a second antenna is measured. Then the CUT is used to transmit, and its reflected power is measured. The power received by the second antenna is again measured. The SE is determined using the same formula, but P_{REF} and P_{CUT} are the power received by the second antenna when the reference antenna and CUT are transmitting, respectively. The $P_{input REF}$ and $P_{input CUT}$ is the power transmitted by the reference antenna and CUT, respectively, after being adjusted by the amount of power which is reflected. Therefore, this method adjusts for the differences in VSWR between the reference antenna and the connector/test fixture.

All testing was performed using the same MIL-STD-38999 size 9 connector torqued to 8 inch-pounds. All testing was performed in the Naval Air Warfare Center Aircraft Division Indianapolis Mode-Stirred Chamber. The dimensions of this chamber are 11'X13'X8'. The stirrer is 5 feet in diameter. The chamber is constructed of zinc plated steel clad panels which are bolted together. The stirrer was continuously rotated (mode-stirred rather than mode-tuned operation) and peak measurements were performed.

Results

The results are shown in Figures 3 through 6. Figure 3 shows the shielding of the connector as measured on Fixture 1 using the Transmit Method. The shielding with and without adjustments for VSWR are shown. Also shown is the shielding of the same connector on the same fixture using the same method after retorquing the connector. The VSWR corrections are at most, 2 dB. The effect of retorquing the connector on shielding is as much as 26 dB. Typically, retorquing a connector does not cause variations in the shielding to be this large, but retorquing does have significant effects on the shielding. Figure 4 shows the shielding of the connector as measured on Fixture 1 using the Receive Method. The second line shows the shielding after retorquing. Again, this effect is significantly more than the VSWR adjustments shown in Figure 3. Figure 5 shows the shielding measured on Fixture 2 using the Receive Method. The differences in shielding measurements on Fixture 1 and Fixture 2 using the Receive Method are due to retorquing of the connector. In order to verify this, the shielding of an artifact which requires no torquing was tested. Its repeatability was within 3 dB, due to measurement system error. Figure 6 shows the shielding as measured on Fixture 2 using the Transmit Method with and without VSWR adjustments. Again, the VSWR correc-

tion was at most, 2 dB. For example, at 9.5 GHz, the VSWR was measured to be 5.2:1, which caused a 2 dB adjustment in the shielding. As seen in the preceding graphs, this is small compared to the repeatability of the connector. A different connector was then tested on the same fixture. The VSWR at 3.5 GHz was measured to be 8.7:1 and the VSWR adjustment affected the shielding by 4 dB. (Results not shown.) This provides some practical data to use in determining a maximum VSWR to allow in the revised MIL-STD-1344 Method 3008.

Conclusions

Adjustments in SE values for VSWR differences between a connector/test fixture and a reference antenna may not increase accuracy since an over-correction would result due to reflections from the chamber surfaces. The reflections contribute to the measured VSWR, but also contribute to the field intensity in the chamber.

If manual measurements are being performed using a continuously rotating stirrer, it is impossible to know the VSWR at the time of maximum transfer between the transmitting device and receiving device. The VSWR at this time is typically less than the average VSWR during one rotation of the stirrer, so SE adjustments would be relatively small.

For connector testing at 1-10 GHz, VSWR adjustments affect the SE values by only 1-2 dB maximum when the VSWR of the connector/test fixture is less than 5:1. This is within measurement system error. This is a small adjustment compared to the repeatability of a connector, which in some cases, is as much as 30 dB. A VSWR of 8.7:1 was found to affect the SE value by 4 dB. This suggests that a maximum VSWR of the connector/test fixture to be allowed in the revised MIL-STD-1344 Method 3008 may be 5:1 or more, but less than 9:1.

References

- [1] MIL-STD-1344A, Notice 2, Method 3008, 14 August 1981.
- [2] ANSI/EIA-364-66-1990, 12 June 1990.
- [3] Michael O. Hatfield, Naval Surface Warfare Center, Dahlgren, Va.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

FIXTURE 1 - TRANSMIT METHOD

Figure 3.

FIXTURE 1 - RECEIVE METHOD

Figure 4.

FIXTURE 2 - RECEIVE METHOD

Figure 5.

FIXTURE 2 - TRANSMIT METHOD

Figure 6.